

This project is co-financed by the European Union

Grant Agreement No.: 824603

Call: H2020-SwafS-2018-1

Type of action: RIA

Starting date: 1/02/2019

ACTION

Live dashboard and media publishing portal 2

Coordinator: CEFRIEL
Quality reviewer: FVB-IGB

Deliverable nature	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package and Task	WP4, Task 4.5
Contractual delivery date	M36 - 31 Jan 2022
Actual delivery date	M36

Authors

Author name	Organization	E-Mail
Damiano Scandolari	Cefriel	damiano.scandolari@cefriel.com
Ilaria Baroni	Cefriel	ilaria.baroni@cefriel.com
Irene Celino	Cefriel	irene.celino@cefriel.com
Esteban González Guardia	UPM	egonzalez@fi.upm.es

Abstract	D4.9 is the advancement of the activities described in D4.8. It contains the updates of the infographic, with a general analysis of the information collected, it contains the implementation details and description of two tools created for the ACTION project, and the contents of the workshop for pilots on data visualization.
Keywords	Dashboard, infographic, data collection, data representation

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable, is written by the ACTION project consortium under EC grant agreement 824603 and does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

How to quote this document

Scandolari, D. Baroni, I., Celino, I., González Guardia, E. (2022), Live dashboard and media publishing portal 2

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1 INTRODUCTION	5
2 LIVE DASHBOARD	6
2.1 Graphical updates	6
2.2 Data collection methodology	8
2.3 Data analysis	9
3 WORKSHOP ON DATA VISUALIZATION	12
4 CONCLUSIONS	14
4 REFERENCES	15

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D4.9 is the update on the activities described in D4.8 on the dashboard and data visualization for the ACTION project.

In this version, there is a specific chapter dedicated to the live infographic with the overview of the major changes, the process to collect the information needed, and the inclusion of the new pilots from the second round of the accelerator, as well as a brief analysis of the data collected during the six months of the accelerator.

The live infographic tool is available on the ACTION website under the specific section “pilot’s factsheet”.

This document also presents the description of the workshop on data visualization, created for the ACTION pilots, to support the dissemination of their project results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Data representation is crucial in citizen science initiatives: both for the pilots, to better explain their results, especially to the authorities and to the citizens, and for projects with an accelerator phase like ACTION, to better summarize the activities performed. Also, this representation can be used to interpret the data produced, identifying patterns on it. This corresponds to the *Interpret data* and *Share and communicate results* steps of the Participatory Science Lifecycle (See Fig. 1) defined by ACTION

Figure 1: Participatory Science Lifecycle

ACTION

In the first deliverable on this topic (Scandolari et al., 2021) a first version of the ACTION dashboard was presented, to illustrate the general ideas based on data collected from the resident pilots and at the end of the first round of the accelerator. Furthermore, a focus on how to create specific dashboards for pilots (using Grafana) was described too.

This document builds on the previous one, collecting all the improvements made during the last months. As far as concerns the dashboard which summarizes pilots' results, further graphical improvements were made, a data collection methodology was implemented, and further analysis on the collected results during the whole second round of the accelerator was described.

Furthermore, to improve the activity related to specific dashboards for pilots as well, a workshop on data visualization was organized, not only to provide the right instruments to the participants, but also to teach them how to create a proper dashboard for their projects.

This document is divided mainly in two sessions, one for the general dashboard on pilots and one for the workshop on data visualization, with the addition of a final chapter to present the conclusions.

2 LIVE DASHBOARD

This chapter collects the main updates for the live dashboard (<https://actionproject.eu/pilotsfactsheet/>) with respect to the previous deliverable. They are related to graphical improvements, a different methodology to collect the information in a more live way, and data analysis.

2.1 Graphical updates

Since its first iteration described in Deliverable 4.8, the design of the dashboard was refined and monthly updated with the newly gathered data to include new participants, assets, events, and objectives.

Figure 2: Infographic section on pilots and SDGs

The “card” style adopted for the first iteration was left unaltered to keep mirroring the ACTION official website’s theme and colours. While some tiles have been moved or resized, the overall structure and storytelling design of the dashboard, developed with the support of a communication designer at Cefriel and finalized with several members of the ACTION’s core team, was left unaltered to ensure continuity between the data shown for the first round of pilots and the newly added information.

The first part, focusing on the pilots, now also includes information regarding the new ones, as shown in Figure 2. The numbers regarding people reached, participants, events, scientific outputs, and articles have been placed in a row and were each given a matching icon to improve readability and to give each information the same relevance.

Consequently, the chart displaying the “*Relevance of the areas of impact according to the pilots*” has been moved down, on the side of the “*Sustainable Development Goals*” one, where new tiles were added to include the new objectives. Regarding the first chart, the colour scale representing the relevance level was changed from red-to-green to grey-to-green, to highlight the areas of major interest and impact for the pilots, rather than focusing on the presence or absence of the pilots effort in each area.

Figure 3: Infographic on active volunteers and ACTION toolkit’s wheel

The following part of the dashboard, where the focus shifts to the citizens involved and the data gathered, was also updated with the new data collected and the links to the new pilots. Most notably, as shown in Figure 3, the ACTION wheel chart was revisited to change the different steps according to the project updates. In this visualization it's important to note how, compared to the first few iterations, there are volunteers involved in every step of the wheel. Aside from the data updates and new links, the remaining part of the dashboard (Figure 4) was not changed.

Figure 4: Volunteers demographics and pilots location

2.2 *Data collection methodology*

During the second round of the accelerator, it was necessary to feed the dashboard monthly. For this reason, the contributions were divided in three main groups:

1. Information from resident pilots
2. Information from accelerated pilots
3. Information on impact

For the first case, for each resident pilot, a person in charge of monthly updating the file set up for the general data collection was selected. In the second case, for each accelerated pilot, a specific file was uploaded on nextcloud, to be updated monthly, and then it was asked to pilot mentors to check the information reported and to insert them in the file for the general data collection. The third type of data, both for resident and accelerated pilots, is referred to the generated impact, which is measured only at the beginning and at the end of the acceleration process. For this reason, it was decided to wait to include this information, and avoid asking it to the different pilots, with the purpose of collecting the necessary data during the impact assessment process and to only update the chart in the dashboard dashboard at the end of the project.

The main file used to collect the information is available on the google drive of the ACTION project and it is divided in four main parts: overview, outputs, impact, file management.

The overview part collects the general information on the pilots (geographical reach, volunteers' information, events, references to the ACTION wheel, etc.). The output sheet is mostly referred to the assets produced, while the impact one is referred to the expected impacts, type of pollution, SDGs, and the file management section which collects information on responsible (pilot manager, mentors, etc.) to fill the table.

For the accelerated pilots, the separated files proposed to each of them has the same structure of the main file, with the exclusion of the impact sheet, as that information will be collected separately. For the timing of the data collection, it was fixed at one gathering per month (with the exception of August), at the same time as the interim update calls for the accelerated pilots, with the addition of one final update at the end of the period.

Pilots were notified one week in advance by mail followed, if needed, by a reminder, and the deadlines to collect the information were the following:

7th of April 2021

5th of May 2021

2nd of June 2021

30th of June 2021

September 2021 for the final update

This process ran smoothly thanks to the support of all the participants.

ACTION

2.3 Data analysis

Thanks to the adoption of the previously described data collection methodology, it was possible to chart trends and changes in the aggregated data to keep track of the status of the project. The following charts represent the data related to the second-round pilots and their change over time, from April to August 2021.

Data collection

Figure 5 represents the data collected over 5 months concerning the number of events organized and the amount of data collected. Both values are represented as a percentage of the total to show growth over time. As the chart suggests, there is a link between the amount of data collected and the number of events organized, during which several collection activities were performed. This highlights the importance of such events in gathering data, engaging citizens and, more in general, piloting the data collection process.

The chart also shows how the curve flattened after June, where the gathering process was ending to make way for the analysis, interpretation. In the last two months, the events focused more on the communication of the results, which is the reason for the difference in growth between the two curves.

Figure 5: Percentage growth of data collection and events organized from April to August

Scientific outputs

As previously mentioned, the data collection process peaked in the first few months, to then make way for data analysis and results communication. This trend is also visible when looking at the number of papers, posters, and other scientific outputs published, with the curve spiking in June, when the pilots were wrapping up the data collection process to analyze, interpret and publish the gathered information (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Total of published scientific outputs

Dissemination activities and people reached

Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively map the growth of the project's reach and the amount of non-scientific articles published. As dissemination activities such as social media posts and published articles are as vital to the success of the project as scientific publications and events, it is important to see that, during this period, the dissemination activity was constant and effective. After the expected initial spike in people reached, the numbers kept growing around a few percentage points per month.

Figure 7: Total people reached per month

Figure 8: Total articles published per month

3 WORKSHOP ON DATA VISUALIZATION

As it has been commented in the introduction, some final steps in a research implementation are the interpretation of the data and the communication of results. This can be usually done by sharing your results in a repository and writing a paper. In the case of citizen science projects, since the results are more oriented to the general public, data visualization plays a crucial role in the communication process. For that, ACTION organized an interactive webinar open to all ACTION pilots, held on June the 10th, 2021, to explain the main concepts of data visualization. This webinar was divided into two sessions: i) a short introduction to data visualization and ii) an introduction to Grafana.

The second session (Figure 9) started with a brief introduction to Grafana¹, an open source platform to create dashboards. This platform has been deployed on the ACTION servers and it is currently available to all pilots². A database was also deployed to store the data of the pilots.

Figure 9. Data visualization

In the first part of this session, some concepts of Grafana were introduced, including different visualizations available in Grafana, how to build a query to get results from ACTION databases, the alarm system and how to include your dashboards in a webpage. The alarm system is used to

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4068095>

² <https://dashboards.dataportal.actionproject.eu/>

D4.9 Live dashboard and media publishing portal 2

notify users of some conditions in the values represented, for example, the monoxide levels are higher than a threshold. These conditions are defined by the dashboard designer.

After this introduction to the platform, we started to *play* with it, using data that had been provided by some pilots and had been already loaded into our databases to be used during the webinar. This webinar was scheduled before the pilots started to work with visualizations so it was an inspiration for them. More information can be found in D2.13 Final Review 2nd Round of the Call.

You can find an example of the dashboard created for the Open Soil Atlas pilot here (Figure 9):

<https://dashboards.dataportal.actionproject.eu/d/aDJANleGk/open-soil-atlas?orgId=1>

Figure 9: Visualizations of Open Soil Atlas

ACTION

4 CONCLUSIONS

The work described in this deliverable fills the gap from the previous activities presented in D4.8 and the progresses made during the second round of the accelerator. In the last year new pilots were involved thanks to the second round of the accelerator, the activities to the continuous improvement of the dashboard were finalized, the data collection was performed, and the workshops to work with pilots were offered to support the activities.

The graphics developed in the dashboard were used to share results of the ACTION project in many events, to represent the diversities and the challenges afforded by the different projects involved. Furthermore, a particular focus is needed on the data analysis provided in this deliverable, which underlines how information grew during the accelerator period.

ACTION

4 REFERENCES

Scandolari Damiano, Baroni Ilaria, Celino Irene, González Guardia Esteban, & Re Calegari Gloria. (2021). D4.8 Live dashboard and publishing portal (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5724561>